

RES4LIVE – Progress on Pilot Systems for Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

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Abstract

The utilization of fossil fuels in agriculture has elevated its status as a significant contributor to Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, thereby impacting global climate change and posing a potential threat to food security. A major contributor to these emissions is intensive livestock farming, a highly energy-consuming sub-sector heavily dependent on fossil fuels. This practice requires a diverse range of energy sources, including electricity and thermal energy for heating and cooling indoor livestock facilities, equipment operation, lighting, and ventilation. The H2020 RES4LIVE project aims to eliminate fossil fuel consumption in certain areas of industrial livestock farming by introducing cost-effective Renewable Energy Sources (RES) technologies, enhancing thermal comfort for animals. The project showcases and evaluates various innovative RES technologies on four European pilot farms with swine (Belgium and Italy), dairy cattle (Germany), and laying hens (Greece). The present study elaborates on the design and installation process of the most distinctive parts of integrated systems (PV/PVT, heat pump, geothermal energy storage, biogas upgrading and biomethane tractor) in the four pilot farms and provides performance results obtained after the first months of their operation. The results add to the existing knowledge on incorporating RES into livestock systems and provide valuable perspectives on the adaptability of the studied systems for use in commercial facilities.

Keywords: Renewable Energy Sources, Intensive livestock farming, Livestock farming de-fossilization, Climate resilience.

1. Introduction

During the last decade, it has become apparent that fossil fuel use in the agricultural domain has negative effects, rendering it a major source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, exacerbating global climate change and risking food security (Dubois et al., 2017; FAO, 2019). The intensive livestock sector remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels, accounting for a substantial portion of energy demand in agriculture (Peyraud and Macleod, 2020). According to recent data, agriculture accounts for 10.3% of the EU's GHG emissions, with the livestock sector alone accounting for around 70% of all GHG emissions (European Court of Auditors, 2021). Direct, i.e., on-farm, energy use accounts for 3.2% of the EU's total energy consumption (Eurostat, 2021). Energy consumption in intensive livestock farming is multifaceted, encompassing both electricity and thermal energy needs, depending on the structures used, the agroclimatic conditions, and the types of livestock used. These requirements range from maintaining optimal environmental conditions within livestock buildings (such as heating, cooling, and ventilation) (Costantino et al., 2016) to powering equipment (e.g., milking process, manure management) (Shine et al., 2020; Loyon, 2018) lighting, and transportation (e.g., tractors). Recognizing these challenges, there has been a growing emphasis on transitioning towards more sustainable practices and reducing dependence on fossil fuels in livestock production. National and EU policy is increasingly focused on improving environmental sustainability and animal welfare of

livestock production. To achieve the goals set out in the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy (EU Commission, 2019; 2020), livestock rearing, and production will need to transform in the coming decades. Advancements in Renewable Energy Sources (RES) technologies, coupled with declining costs and improved reliability, have created new opportunities to embrace renewable energy production (Paris et al., 2022). Established technologies, such as solar photovoltaic (PV) panels, and biomass/biogas systems are among the RES technologies increasingly adopted by farmers to meet their energy needs (Majeed et al., 2023), while more ascending ones, such as Thermal-Photovoltaics (PVT), heat pumps (HP), are attracting interest. The H2020 RES4LIVE project contributes to the effort of fossil fuel-free agriculture by developing and assessing the performance of innovative RES systems for the livestock sector in four European pilot farms. In the following sections, the main parts of the completed systems, as well as their first performance results, are presented.

2. Pilot Farms and Integrated Renewable Energy Sources (RES) Systems

Towards the imperative for de-fossilized livestock farming, within the framework of RES4LIVE, the design, installation, testing, and monitoring of different integrated RES systems is realized. The integrated systems have been specifically designed to fit the needs of each pilot farm, aiming at an optimal combination of adapted and commercial Renewable Energy Sources (RES) solutions. The developed units are fine-tuned by a smart control system, to achieve minimisation of fossil fuels-based energy, while enhancing the welfare of hosted animals. In the following sections, the design and installation process of the most distinctive parts of integrated systems in the four pilot farms are presented, alongside the performance results obtained after the first months of their operation.

2.1. EV ILVO swine farm in Belgium – PVT and Multi-Source Heat Pumps

The farm “Varkenscampus” is managed by EV ILVO, UGENT, and HoGent for research and educational purposes alongside normal commercial production. It is a farrow-to-finish pig farm hosting at any moment sows, piglets, and fattening pigs. The RES4LIVE installations include:

- i. an 8.4 kWp PVT system accompanied by a Solar Station (see below), connected to the short-term thermal energy storage (TES) tank
- ii. two multi-source HPs, high - and low-temperature
- iii. a smart control system for the RES systems and the ventilation in one fattening pig room, as well as environmental sensors and energy meters

Figure 1. The PVT system (left) and HPs (right) at EV ILVO farm.

The PVT system and HPs (Figure 1) provide heat and power to the entire facility. The developed two multi-source, modular HPs substitute a 60 kW gas condensing boiler. They can provide heating at different temperature levels, and cooling. The low-temperature (25kW) will provide floor heating (42°C), while the high-temperature (40kW) will provide air heating and domestic hot water (60°C). The HPs are coupled with the PVT system through a short-term TES tank to enhance their Coefficient of Performance (COP). Furthermore, in the case that solar energy will not suffice to cover the required thermal load at the evaporator, a dry cooler will also be available. The high-temperature HP will also make it possible to cool in the fattening pigs' compartments and nursery. Therefore, cold water will go through the twin tubes of the air heating system.

The developed solar pumping circuit, or “Solar Central”, is a standardised group of components that operate and run the PVT system in an optimized way to deliver heat and electricity to the required

integration point. The solar thermal circuit delivers the heat down from the PVT collectors to the solar station, which is coupled with the heat storage, or fitted with a heat exchanger, depending on the case. In all RES4LIVE interventions including PVT systems, the developed solar central concept is incorporated.

2.2. GOLINELLI swine farm in Italy – PVT, BTES, and Multi-Source Heat Pump

The second pilot farm is the commercial pig farm GOLINELLI located in the Modena province, Italy. The farm consists of a farrowing barn, a nursery barn, a gestation barn, and a hog barn with a gestation sector. The interventions include (Figure 2):

- i. a 7.68 kW_{el}, 25 kW_{th} PVT system accompanied with a solar station
- ii. a Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES) system, storing the excess heat from the PVT system
- iii. a multi-source, medium-temperature HP of 35 kW
- iv. environmental sensors and energy meters

Figure 2. The PVT system (left), BTES system (middle), and HP (right) at GOLINELLI farm.

The HP unit was designed to substitute a 34 kW LPG boiler providing hot water to the space heating system of the nursery barn. The PVT collectors are connected to the solar central which is the main operational pumping unit with the control system to operate the PVTs. The Solar Central is connected to the BTES system to store the heat produced over an extended period. This way, heat is flowing from the PVTs to the HPs through the BTES system, while the ambient heat is exploited through an air dry cooler. The HP is a multi-source one, selecting between ground and air heat by activating and deactivating the fans. To achieve increased COPs, the source selection between ground and air is based on the comparison between the geothermal fluid return temperature T_g and the two temperature thresholds decided by the user, T_a and T_b , in the following manner:

- $T_g > T_a$ - Operates as a Ground-source HP. The two fans are deactivated, and the geothermal pump is active
- $T_b < T_g < T_a$ - Operates as a Dual-source HP. The fans are activated and the whole system is active
- $T_g < T_b$ - Operates as an Air-source HP. The geothermal pump is deactivated, while the fans remain active

2.3. AUA laying hens farm in Greece – PV and Heat Pump

The experimental poultry farm for egg production has been established on the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) campus and occupies an area of 90 m², hosting approximately 400 animals at least. It is further divided into two separate equally sized rooms, pullets' and a laying hens' house. Both pullets and hens are raised in a 3-tier colony cage production system. Hens are housed in enriched cages. The RES4LIVE system (Figure 3) includes:

- i. a 10 kW HP, for heating, cooling, and dehumidification
- ii. a 9 kWp standard PV system, on the rooftop of a nearby building
- iii. smart control and new LED systems

Figure 3. The PV system (left) and HP (right) at AUA farm.

Before the project's interventions, the facility relied mainly on forced ventilation to remove the thermal loads, applied with direct drive fans in both rooms, while the pullets' house used to be heated only by infrared heating lamps. The goal of the project's main interventions is twofold; first, they aim at enhancing the thermal comfort of the hosted animals by regulating the indoor air quality, temperature, and relative humidity with the use of HP. Keeping the temperature and relative humidity, ideally, in the thermo-neutral zone, or thermal comfort zone, is determining for animal welfare and increased production. Second, to minimize the electricity consumption from the electricity grid.

2.4. LVAT dairy farm in Germany – Bio-CNG Plant and Retrofitted Biomethane Tractor

The Educational and Experimental Centre for Animal Breeding and Husbandry (LVAT) is located in Groß Kreutz, in Brandenburg, Germany. The farm includes three barns for milk production, with an overall number of 445 cows and calves. The produced manure feeds an existing biogas plant of 1000 Nm³ per day capacity, combined heat, and power (CHP) generation. Within RES4LIVE, the following RES interventions are demonstrated (Figure 4):

- i. a biogas to biomethane upgrading unit, equipped with a fuel-filling station,
- ii. a diesel farm tractor retrofitted for biomethane use
- iii. an innovative PVT system for decentralized heat and electrical power generation, coupled with a Solar Station and an existing milk cooling system
- iv. a smart system for barn climate control based on ventilation tubes, using pre-cooled air for evaporative cooling
- v. a smart management and control system to efficiently control heat and electricity consumption

Figure 4. The Bio-CNG plant and filling station (left) and the biomethane tractor at the LVAT farm.

The new, small-scale (5 Nm³ h⁻¹ biomethane) technological setup with a hollow fiber membrane in the very low-pressure range (7-8 bar) and a hybrid compression was set up. In a one-stage membrane separation process, methane (CH₄) is extracted from raw biogas. Using a closed cycle concept, this process ensures that only methane is produced and compressed as BioCNG (Compressed Natural Gas) for use as fuel. All CO₂-containing gas from the membrane separation process is fed back into the raw biogas storage. Moreover, the unit incorporated a Bio-CNG filling station characterized by a simplified and compact design in terms of the compression process.

One of the farm’s diesel tractors was also modified for BioCNG use. Its engine, with a nominal power of 59 kW, was converted from diesel to biomethane to provide the same torque and power after the conversion and handle the same duty cycle, mainly for food mixing and delivery. Multiple aspects were considered, including the thermal stress of the engine to keep with the reliability of the diesel engine, the reduction of the exhaust emissions, the compactness of the gas tank system, containing 26 kg of biomethane, and the design-to-cost objective of the modification, aiming at reusing the maximum number of the diesel parts.

3. RES Systems’ Performance Results and Discussion

The installation and commissioning of the RES systems were followed by a period of monitoring and fine-tuning. The sections below present the preliminary performance results of the main systems at each pilot farm. The availability of logged data in each case was influenced by the managerial schedules of the respective farms.

3.1. EV ILVO RES Systems Performance

After a series of tests, the high-temperature HP effectively maintains the setpoint of 60°C, providing sanitary hot water and air heating. The low-temperature HP, with a setpoint temperature of 42°C, is connected only to the underfloor heating system used for piglets. The utilization of two HPs appears to be beneficial to the efficiency of the system, as compared to the original installation. Before the project, a natural gas boiler provided water at 70°C for all subsystems, and afterwards, it was cooled down to 42°C for the underfloor heating, losing valuable heat in the process.

When the temperature of the TES tank is above 37°C, the HPs operate as water-to-water, until the temperature drops below 17°C. Below this point, the dry cooler serves as a heat source for the HPs using either one or two fans, depending on the heat demand, thus operating as air-to-water. The PVTs’ heating circuit operates only when solar irradiance is higher than 200 W/m² for longer than 60 seconds, providing the TES tank with heat. The HPs’ water temperature variation alongside the outdoor temperature and irradiance between 07 and 28/05/2024 are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Environmental conditions and HPs’ water temperature variation at EV ILVO farm, between 07/05 and 28/05/2024.

During the most recent tests that took place between 07/05 and 28/05/2024, the overall system performed as intended. The HPs operated longer as water-to-water compared to previous test periods, as solar irradiance was increased during May. The power consumption and heating capacity of both HPs are presented in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. Power consumption and heating capacity of the high- and low-temperature HPs at the EV ILVO farm, between 07/05 and 28/05/2024.

The low-temperature HP appears to be slightly oversized, operating at a lower compressor capacity, which negatively influences the part load ratio of the HP. The high-temperature HP, though continuously going into ON/OFF mode, performs well. During this testing phase, the system operated for 85% in the air-water and 15% in the water-water mode, respectively. During the air-water mode, the average COP of the high-temperature is estimated at 2.95, while for the low-temperature HP, the

COP is 4.87. During water-water operation, the high- and low-temperature HPs use considerably less electricity, increasing their COPs to 9.85 and 4.10, respectively. The solar electricity was being logged from the 7th of May but stopped on the 14th. During these seven days, the PVTs contributed 0.25 MWh or 18% electricity, entailing about 18% of the electricity demand of the HPs (1.37 MWh).

3.2. GOLINELLI RES Systems Performance

To analyse the performance of the PVT-HP-BTES system at GOLINELLI farm, a representative period, between the 10th and 25th of April 2024 was chosen. Between the 10th and 17th, where the average temperature and irradiance were higher than usual (above 20°C and 300 W m⁻², respectively), the PVT and the solar central station both were activated, and solar heat was injected into the BTES system. From the 17th to the 25th, the weather temperature dropped abruptly, with the presence of precipitation, and reduced irradiance. The average weather temperature reduced to 11°C, with low peaks down to 2.5°C during the night. During this period, high variability of weather temperature occurred (Figure 7). In these conditions, the hallway of the piglets' building started to drop its ambient temperature and the HP was automatically activated to provide the necessary comfort, by extracting the heat from the borehole heat exchangers (BHE) of the BTES and, working in hybrid mode, from the ambient air. The two consecutive periods are representative then of the sequence injection-extraction of the PVT-BTES-HP system.

Figure 7. Frequency distribution of outdoor/indoor temperature between 17/04 and 24/04/2024 in GOLINELLI farm.

From the monitoring system, it was possible to record the values from various sensor temperatures on the PVT and the BTES circuit. The calculated stored energy was around 2160 MJ, equal to 600 kWh. The HP extracts energy from the BTES to cover the needs of the hallway of the piglets' building. At the moment, the HP works only in heating mode, but it is designed for cooling as well. For most of the testing period, the HP was able to keep the temperature of the hallway very close to the desired setpoint temperature, being activated for 17.4% of the total time. The measured temperature data in the hallway are present in Figure 7 as well. The heating fluid temperature and the cumulative energy provided are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Energy provided to the hallway by the HP in the period 17/04 and 25/04/2024 (grey), and related inlet and outlet temperatures (blue and red).

The total energy provided by the HP to the building was around 1200 kWh, and the electric energy used was around 300 kWh. The total heat provided during the Ground mode was about 670 kWh (approx. 75%), while the remaining 230 kWh were extracted during the Hybrid Mode (approx. 25%). The Hybrid mode was necessary mostly during the night when temperatures were lower. The Air mode was not activated during this testing period. In conclusion, the average COPs for each mode of the HP for the period between 17 and 25/04/2024 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Average COP of the HP in the reference period 17/04 and 25/04/2024.

HP mode	Average COP
Ground	4.67
Air	(not activated during this period)
Hybrid	3.50
Overall	4.34

3.3. AUA RES Systems Performance

Though the installations were completed earlier, the integrated RES system in the AUA poultry farm became fully operational in May 2023 when a new laying hen batch arrived. The data analysed during two characteristic periods, summer and winter, are presented and discussed next. In both, only the laying hens' room was operational, with the HP operating in one mode each time, cooling, and heating, respectively. In Table 2, the total amount of energy consumed by the facility as well as that produced by the PVs, and the Seasonal COP (SCOP) of the HP, are presented for both periods.

Table 2. Energy and HP performance-related data for the AUA pilot farm.

Period (mode)	Total electricity used (kWh)	Total electricity produced (kWh)	Self-sufficiency (%)	Seasonal COP
Summer (cooling)	4,031.23	908.50	22.54	2.42
Winter (heating)	2,389.52	482.71	20.20	3.65

Indicative figures are presented for the period between 30/07 and 09/08/2023. Despite the summer of 2023 being one of the warmest of the last years in Greece, the HP regulated the indoor temperature effectively (Figure 9). The profile for power consumption and PV power production for an indicative period in summer (23-25/07/2024) are presented in Figure 10 below.

Figure 9. Indoor temperature regulation by the AUA pilot farm HP between 30/07 and 09/08/2023.

Figure 10. Power consumption and PV power production profile of the AUA pilot farm for an indicative period in summer (23-25/07/2023).

3.4. LVAT RES Systems Performance

The commissioning of the BioCNG plant at LVAT took place between 19/07 and 21/07/2023, and the data collection began. The first data evaluation was based on 20-second intervals, but up to 4-second intervals are possible and were used for technical optimization of the system. In Figure 11 graphs represent the first data acquired, while Table 3 illustrates the main performance indicators of the plant.

Figure 11. BioCNG plant power consumption (top), BioCNG flow rate (middle), and CH₄ concentration of BioCNG (bottom) at the LVAT pilot farm.

Table 3. Key performance indicators from the data monitoring of the LVAT biogas upgrading pilot plant.

Performance indicator	Average
Specific energy consumption [$\text{kWh}_{\text{el}} \text{Nm}^{-3} \text{BioCNG}$]	0,94
Separation pressure hollow fiber membrane [bar]	7,83
Separation temperature hollow fiber membrane [°C]	57,44
Methane concentration [%]	96,75
Start-up time until BioCNG production [min]	26,78

Initially, a two-week testing period took place, using the biomethane tractor mainly for transport operations. Indicative data of the tractor speed are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Tractor speed during the first tests at LVAT premises.

After analysing the data of this period, the biomethane tractor presented an average fuel consumption of approximately 4.5 kg BioCNG per hour of operation, or 15.75 kg BioCNG daily, for approximately 3.5 hours of operation.

4. Conclusions

The results obtained during the first months of the RES systems operation largely appear satisfactory. Of course, further experimentation and finetuning are in progress to optimize their performance on-farm. The installed RES technologies are further monitored in each pilot farm to draw

solid techno-economic figures for their overall performance. Each integrated system is assessed in terms of technical, environmental, and economic performance, as well as social acceptance. The next steps of the project concern the communication of the outcome that this ongoing work will bring. Their dissemination will concern – besides the scientific community – relevant stakeholders involved in livestock farming, and intensive agriculture in general, with the aim to add to the existing knowledge on incorporating RES into livestock systems and provide valuable perspectives on the adaptability of the studied systems for use in commercial facilities.

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